

EAGLE - Medomrežje *Europeana* antične grške in latinske epigrafike. Digitalni dostop do antičnih napisnih spomenikov

Anja Ragolič, ZRC SAZU, Inštitut za arheologijo

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**Filozofska fakulteta, Univerza v Ljubljani
29. 9. 2016**

9 in ansa vasis aerei magni, quod in ima parte intus habet emblemata argenteum Medusae operis eximii, Inscriptiones ambae sunt in manubrii parte superiore collocatae ita ut infra exhibentur. Rep. in alveo fluvii Laibach [Gratz Iohanneum].

P · CIP · NICOMACHI

SORS · MERCVRI

A. Letius D. L.

RUF. II.

Man Lius

Q. P. L.

Severo

hoc est
 Aulus Letius D. L.
 Libertus. Rufus
 filius Manlius
 Quaesitor potestatis
 auro Severo.

prostat in domo D. ab Othaimb L. P. - juxta flumina
 qui domum alunt. servit pro lavatione - vix
 legi potest totus attribit.

Eagle - konzorcij

No	Name	Short name	Country
1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA	UNIROMA1	Italy
2	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI BARI "ALDO MORO"	UNIBA	Italy
3	RUPRECHT-KARLS-UNIVERSITAET HEIDELBERG	UHEI	Germany
4	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UOXF	United Kingdom
5	UNIVERSIDAD DE ALCALA	UAH	Spain
6	PARIS-LODRON-UNIVERSITÄT SALZBURG	PLUS	Austria
7	UNIVERSITATEA BABES BOLYAI	UBB	Romania
8	EÖTVÖS LORÁND TUDOMÁNYEGYETEM	ELTE	Hungary
9	SVEUCILISTE JURJA DOBRILE U PULI	UNIPU	Croatia
10	ZNANSTVENORAZISKOVALNI CENTER SLOVENSKE AKADEMIJE ZNANOSTI IN UMETNOSTI	ZRC SAZU	Slovenia
11	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	AUSONIUS	France
12	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	K.U.LEUVEN	Belgium
13	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CNR-ISTI	Italy
14	DEUTSCHES ARCHAOLOGISCHES INSTITUT	DAI	Germany
15	THE CYPRUS RESEARCH AND EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATION	CYI	Cyprus
16	EUREVA SAS	EUREVA	France
17	THE BRITISH SCHOOL AT ROME	BSR	Italy
18	GOGATE SRL	GOGATE	Italy
19	PROMOTER SRL	PROMOTER	Italy

TOTAL	1.472.198	1.555.205
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Elektronske baze

- Epigraphic Database Roma - EDR
- Heidelberška epigrafska baza – EDH
- Hispania Epigraphica online
- Epigrafske podatkovna baza Bari

epigrafska baza projekta Eagle - Europeana

BETA

Text (159)

Only items with links to media

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Znanstvenoraziskovalni center Slovenske akademije znanosti in umetnosti (159)

Inscription from Emona

L(ucius) Cantius / L(uci) l(ibertus) Fidus v(ivus) f(ecit) / sibi et Cantiae / f(iliae) Cantiae / Europae l(ib)ertae / Optatae / an(norum) VI

(Local) Stone

[View at Znanstvenoraziskovalni center Slovenske akademije znanosti in umetnosti](#) ↗

■ Text

[Inscription from Emona](#)

THE DISAPPEARING TOMBSTONE AND OTHER STORIES FROM EMONA

MARJETA ŠAŠEL KOS

p M
ryt
u/

Back

Name : EDR000023

Transcription : [A(ulus)] Novius A(uli) l(ibertus)
?Philargurus?
Opetreia P(ubli) l(iberta) Secunda.
parte CXXV.

Type of Inscription : [sepulcralis](#)

Type of Object : [unknown](#)

Type of Entity : visual

Ancient find place (City) : Roma

Konference in sestanki projekta

- Rome – 27-29/01/2016: [EAGLE 2016 International Conference](#)
- Bari – 23-25/09/2015: [Sixth EAGLE International Event 2015](#)
- Nicosia – 11-12/03/2015: [Fifth EAGLE International Event 2015](#)
- Paris – 29-30/09/2014, 01/10/2014: [EAGLE 2014 International Conference](#)
- Bologna – 29/05/2014: [EAGLE – EpiDoc Workshop](#)
- Rome – 16/05/2014: [Best Practices for the Fruition and Promotion of Cultural Heritage: EAGLE & Wiki Loves Monuments & Award Ceremony Wiki Loves Monuments Italia](#)
- Ljubljana – 19-20/02/2014: [First EAGLE International Event 2014](#)
- Rome – 02/04/2013: [EAGLE Kick-off meeting](#)

Vloga ZRC SAZU

Epigraphic Archives of Slovenia (ZRC-SAZU)						
Date	D-Net		Total	Europeana		
	artefact	visual		CHO	WebResources	Total
Mar	269	300	569	269	76	345

History and comments:

- The ZRC-SAZU content due to the MS16 is of 400 items.
- At March ZRC-SAZU sent to EAGLE 269 artefacts and 300 visual representations for a total of 569 items.
- In Europeana (Europeana ID: 2058817) have been published 269 artefacts and 300 visual representations.
- The CP reached and overcame the amount of data declared in the DoW.

Fig. 5.9 shows one of the important inscriptions provided by ZRC-SAZU to the EAGLE portal and to Europeana.

Predstavitve, predavanja, knjiga...

- RAGOLIČ, Anja. **Medmrežje Europeana antične grške in latinske epigrafike (EAGLE)** predavanje na posvetovanju "*Digitalne vsebine: nastanek, hranjenje in dostop*", 5. jun. 2014
- RAGOLIČ, Anja. Epigraphy as a tool for learning Latin : the case of the Prežihov Voranc Primary School in Ljubljana, Slovenia. V: ORLANDI, Silvia (ur.). *Information technologies for epigraphy and cultural heritage : proceedings of the first EAGLE international conference*, (Collana Convegni, 26). Sapienza: Università Editrice, 2014
- ŠAŠEL KOS, Marjeta. The Disappearing tombstone and other stories from Emona, *Bari, september 24 – 25, 2015*
- ŠAŠEL KOS, Marjeta. Izginjajoči nagrobnik in druge zgodbe iz Emone / The Disappearing Tombstone and Other Stories from Emona. Ljubljana 2015.

Virtualna razstava

- <http://webgl-eagle.d4science.org/>
- (soba 4)

IDEA - The International Digital Epigraphy Association

- ustanovitev 9. 5. 2016
- ohranjevanje, dopolnjevanje in nadgradnja dosedanjega znanja
- Cilji:
 - Širjenje in razvijanje raziskovalnih metodologij in publikacij epigrafskih spomenikov, zlasti antičnih
 - Obogatitev in širjenje rezultatov projekta Eagle
- Pisa: 28. September 2016